

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CREATIVE THINKING IN MUSIC EDUCATION

Saddinov Alisher Atadjanovich

Independent researcher, Urganch State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18465280>

Abstract: This article sheds light on the theoretical foundations for developing students' creative thinking in the process of music education. The concept of creative thinking, its pedagogical-psychological essence, and its importance in music education are analyzed. Additionally, the necessity of developing creative thinking in the professional formation of future music teachers is justified.

Keywords: music education, creative thinking, artistic creation, student, professional competence, pedagogical process.

Introduction

In the context of current globalization processes and the modernization of the education system, there is a need in society for highly qualified specialists who are creative, independent thinkers, and possess an innovative approach. This demand is particularly pressing in the field of art and music education, necessitating the modernization of educational content and teaching technologies in this area to meet contemporary requirements. Today, the development of students' creative thinking in the music education process is considered one of the important problems of pedagogical theory and practice. The professional activity of a future music teacher requires the organic harmony of performing, analytical, and pedagogical creativity. Therefore, it is an important pedagogical task to develop students' skills in deeply perceiving musical works, analyzing their artistic-aesthetic characteristics, and independently interpreting them.

The issue of strengthening the practical component of music education is also being supported at the level of state policy. In particular, in accordance with Presidential Decree No. PQ-112 of February 2, 2022, "On Additional Measures to Further Develop the Field of Culture and the Arts," measures" PQ-112 decision, the organization of instrumental performance classes within the music subject is stipulated for general secondary education institutions. [1] This decision serves to develop students' performance skills, enrich the practical content of music education, and increase interest in the national musical heritage. From this perspective, limiting oneself to traditional teaching methods in the educational process may hinder students from fully realizing their creative potential. Conversely, the application of modern pedagogical approaches, interactive methods, and educational technologies based on creative activities stimulates students' musical thinking processes, fostering their interest in independent research and creative work.

Literature review and methods.

The issue of developing students' creative thinking in music education has been addressed from various perspectives in scientific studies conducted in modern pedagogy, psychology, and art education. First, the individual's semantic-meaning field and motivation are interpreted as the central factors in the development of creativity. In particular, in his

activity theory, A.N. Leontyev reveals the psychological foundations of creative activity, explaining the concept of “meaning” as a complex relationship between the activity's motive and goal [2]. This approach also indicates that in creative musical activity, the student's internal need, personal interest, and individual content play a leading role.

The issue of developing the creative abilities and thinking of future music education teachers has become the focus of research by scientists from the CIS countries and Uzbekistan. In particular, the works of X.X. Batchayeva, O.S. Bogdanova, L.I. Bojovich, V.V. Davidov, A.A. Lublinskaya, The scientific works of B.S. Muxina and others have provided an in-depth analysis of the psychological and pedagogical foundations of creativity, the conditions for fostering a creative approach in learning activities, and the development of the student as an active subject [3]. In these studies, creative thinking is considered a process related to the independent processing, new interpretation, and application of knowledge in practical activity, rather than its mechanical acquisition.

Among local researchers, Z.T. Hasanov, D.M. Mallayev and others explain the emergence of indifference and creative passivity among young people by the weakness of value transmission mechanisms, alienation from cultural heritage, and the insufficient implementation of aesthetic education. Their research particularly emphasizes the need to restore creativity, spiritual and moral values, and to enrich an individual's inner world through the means of art and culture. This demonstrates the musical education's importance not only professionally but also in terms of its educational and spiritual value. A number of scientific studies have extensively covered the ethical, aesthetic, and creative potential of art, particularly in artistic-pedagogical activity. In particular, V.P. Anisimov, S.S. Brikunov, O.S. Bulatova, and E.A. Medvedeva have substantiated the moral potential of art in the upbringing of schoolchildren, while N.Y. Sergeyeva and J.S. Valeeva have scientifically substantiated the important role of art pedagogy, creative methods, and reflective approaches in the professional training of future teachers.

These perspectives serve as an important theoretical source for defining the pedagogical mechanisms of fostering creative thinking in music education. At the same time, in the modern education system, digital technologies, innovative methods, and critical and systemic approaches are recognized as effective tools for developing creative thinking in students. Research on developing a bioethical culture has shown that digital educational technologies accelerate cognitive processes, provide free access to extensive information resources, and enhance independent and analytical thinking [6]. These studies theoretically justify the need to use modern digital music programs, multimedia tools, and interactive platforms in music education. Although existing scientific literature has shed light on the theoretical foundations of the individual's semantic field, creativity psychology, art pedagogy, and digital and innovative educational technologies, the issue of developing students' creative thinking in a comprehensive, systematic, and methodical way specifically in the music education process has not been researched in sufficient depth. This research is aimed at filling this scientific gap and identifying effective pedagogical conditions and methods for developing creative thinking in music education.

Results and discussion

During the research, the effectiveness of the pedagogical conditions, methods, and educational technologies aimed at developing students' creative thinking in music education was determined through experimental work. During the experiment, students' creative activity, musical thinking, and abilities for independent analysis and interpretation were assessed using diagnostic methods. The study conducted a comparative analysis of traditional and modern approaches, determining their impact on the students' creative development. The results of the experimental work showed that, systematic use of interactive methods, creative assignments, music analysis-based lessons, and digital music technologies in the educational process is highly effective in developing students' creative thinking. In particular, the independent analysis of musical works, applying improvisational elements, comparative study of different performance styles, and lessons based on multimedia tools positively contributed to developing students' skills in deeply perceiving and freely interpreting musical images.

The results obtained confirm a significant increase in students' levels of creative activity. Students in the experimental group showed a tendency to make independent decisions when carrying out musical tasks, to approach problematic situations creatively, and to freely express their musical ideas. In particular, studying examples of national music based on modern performance and pedagogical approaches serves as an important factor in increasing students' professional motivation.

The discussion of the results shows that creative thinking is not limited to the development of technical performance skills but is organically connected to an individual's semantic sphere, aesthetic taste, and reflective activity. During the experiment, it was found that students' tendency to express personal attitudes when analyzing musical works and their efforts to interpret the author's idea individually increased. This situation practically confirms A.N. Leontyev's theory of activity and his views on the leading role of motivation in creative activity. Additionally, the use of digital music programs and multimedia tools was observed to serve in activating students' musical thinking, developing their auditory memory, and deepening their analytical thinking processes. The emergence of innovative approaches, artistic independence, and individual stylistic elements in the musical interpretations and creative works produced by the students confirms the importance of innovative technologies in the educational process. Overall, the results of the pilot study indicated that the integration of pedagogical, psychological, and technological factors is crucial for developing students' creative thinking in the music education process. This approach enhances the professional competence of future music teachers, realizes their creative potential, and expands opportunities for innovative activity in the educational process.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research results indicate that developing students' creative thinking in the music education process requires the systematic and purposeful application of modern pedagogical approaches. The theoretical analysis and pilot study confirmed that creative thinking is organically linked not only to a student's performance skills but also to their semantic sphere, motivation, aesthetic taste, and ability to think independently. Furthermore, studying the national musical heritage using modern pedagogical technologies is of great importance, as it enhances students' professional motivation, develops their performance and pedagogical competence, and increases the educational significance of music education. The research findings scientifically substantiate the necessity of forming a creative approach in the

professional training of future music teachers. Overall, this study identifies the pedagogical conditions for developing students' creative thinking in music education. -conditions and effective methods for developing students' creative thinking in music education, presenting important theoretical conclusions and contributing to the development of scientific-practical recommendations for application in educational practice.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 2-fevraldagi "Madaniyat va san'at sohasini yanada rivojlantirishga doir qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi PQ-112-son Qarori
2. Леонтьев А.Н. Проблемы развития психики. – М.: АПН РСФСР, 1959.,13-б. (1. Leontiev A.N. Problems of the development of the psyche. - М.: APN RSFSR, 1959., 13-p.)
3. Е.В.Таранова., Методология артпедагогика в контексте современных междисциплинарных исследований образования.,Научный вестник. –М, 2017 – 47 с.(3. E.V. Taranova., Methodology of art pedagogy in the context of modern interdisciplinary research in education., Scientific Bulletin. -М, 2017 - 47 p.)
4. Педагогика назарияси ва тарихи. 1қисм. Педагогика назарияси. Олий ўқув юртлари учун дарслик./ М.Х.Тохтаходжаеванинг умумий тахрири остида. "Иқтисод-молия", 2007.- 380 б.
4. Насритдинова, М. Н. (2022). МУСИҚА ИНСОНИАТГА НИМА УЧУН КЕРАК?. Science and innovation, 1(Special Issue 2), 577-580. (Nasritdinova, M. N. (2022). WHAT DOES HUMANITY NEED MUSIC FOR?. Science and innovation, 1(Special Issue 2), 577-580.)
5. Ливанова Т. История западно-европейской музыки до1789. Вып. 1-2. 1983
6. Abdullaeva K.M. Maxsus fanlarni o'qitishda bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy bilim va ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning metodik asoslari: Ped.fan.nom.diss. avtoreferati. –Т.: -2006. [Abdullaeva K.M. Methodological basis of the formation of professional knowledge and skills of teachers: Ped.fan.nom.diss. avtoreferati. - Т.: - 2006.]